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**Of Feminine Bodies, the Earth's Wounds, and the
Marginalized Voice: An Ecofeminist Reimagining of
*The Color Purple***

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Abstract: *The feminist writer Simone de Beauvoir first proposed the idea of “Woman as Other” in her pioneering text *The Second Sex*, a core concept in feminist philosophy. She argued that the attributes given to women are not natural, but rather socially constructed. It is the man who stands at the apex of being and relegates the woman to the position of the other. She further asserted that a woman is not born, but rather becomes; her identity is shaped within a patriarchal society that convinces her of her inferiority. In such a society, women are conditioned to forget their own rights, and make to believe that mere existence is the essence of life. In the latter half of the twentieth century, ecofeminism emerged as a branch of feminist thought, exploring the intersection between the exploitation of women and the degradation of nature. Ecofeminists questioned the parallel exploitation and control of nature and women under the gaze of patriarchy. This paper seeks to highlight how nature and women are parallelly wounded by the patriarchal forces and how resistance has emerged from both these realms over time in Alice Walker’s novel *The Color Purple*.*

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The history of women's suffering and subjugation stretches back to the dawn of humanity. In the primordial tale of creation, Eve is portrayed as both inferior and frail. The basis of oppression, repression and exploitation are inherent in the very nature of society. Over the course of time, many female critics and writers have tried to investigate the roots of women's subordination, and they have written about this in their writing. These explorations would provide the groundwork for feminist thinking. The renowned feminist theorist Simone de Beauvoir reveals how women are given attributes that identify them as the 'Other'. In the prelude to *The Second Sex*, she articulates, "She is defined and differentiated with reference to man and not he with reference to her; she is the incidental, the inessential, as opposed to the essential. He is the Subject; he is the Absolute - she is the Other" (16). Yet it is Virginia Woolf, an early and pioneering feminist thinker, who laid the cornerstone for feminist criticism in her seminal work *A Room of One's Own*. In this work, she boldly proclaimed that "men have treated women, and continue to treat them, as inferiors. It is the male, she asserted, who defines what it means to be female and who controls the political, economic, social, and literary structures" (Bressler 104).

At the beginning of human civilization, humanity enjoyed a delicate communion with nature, where all living beings were intricately interconnected and interdependent. Humans, in this primal state, were "neither better nor worse than other creatures (animals, plants, bacteria, rocks, rivers) but simply equal to everything else in the natural world" (Campbell 128). However, this delicate balance was shattered with the human evolution and the advance of science. Man's bond with nature, along with his perception of it, underwent a great sea change, particularly after the industrial revolution. By the latter half of the 20th century, awareness about the shattered relationship between humankind and the environment and the repercussions it had grew, giving birth to a new field of study i.e. *Ecocriticism* aiming at rekindling an appreciation of the symbiotic bond between humanity and nature. The movement found its roots in the publication of Rachel

Carson's *Silent Spring*, and soon blossomed in tandem with the civil rights and women's movements. During this moment of ecological awakening, ecofeminism appeared in the 1970s as a social and political movement focused on women's connections with ecology.

Ecofeminists assert that in this materialistic and patriarchal society, both women and nature endure exploitation. Women are subjugated, while nature is ravaged under the guise of progress and modernization. Francoise d'Eaubonne first introduced the term Ecofeminism in her book *Le Feminisme ou la Mort* in 1974. Karen J. Warren opines that "ecological feminism is the position that there are important connections - historical, experiential, symbolic, theoretical - between the domination of women and the domination of nature, an understanding of which is crucial to both feminism and environmental ethics" (325). Susan Griffin argues that women are in fact unique in proximity to nature, which men simply cannot reach, and the result is a profound balance between women and nature. The core of ecofeminism is the notion that all things are interdependent and interconnected where no hierarchies exist but only share mutual respect. As a Black writer, Alice Walker seeks to elevate the status of Black women by awakening them to their rights and envisioning a world rooted in equality for all living beings. In her novel *The Color Purple*, Walker explores the prevailing hierarchical structures of a male-dominated society, exposing how binary oppositions position women and nature as inferior and vulnerable to exploitation. Through her work, she emphasizes the awakening of Black women's self-awareness and their journey toward autonomy. Walker envisions a utopian society where humans and nature co-exist in peaceful consonance without disturbing each other that reveals their interconnection as it intertwines the themes of race, gender, and nature.

In *The Color Purple*, Alice Walker conveys her deep and abiding concern for the oppression of Black women, particularly as it pertains to their race and sex. In her writings, she explores the world of women where they are considered as objects, not human

beings; devoid of rights and agency. Women are made to be passive victims of patriarchy and male chauvinism, becoming such powerless that they cannot even voice of their own sentiments to anyone else. Celie, the protagonist of the novel, raped by her stepfather at the age of fourteen, and then became a mother of two children. She had been continuously raped and tortured by him, but she was unable to express it to others. She felt numb, emotionally detached, amid the looming threat of violence and fear. She then started to write up her murky experiences to God. The novel begins with a cryptic note that tells the inward agony of Celie:

“You better not never tell nobody but God. It’d kill your mammy.” (03)

She had even been raped during her period, and when she cried out in pain, she was silenced with threats, left to endure the agony in silence. Her father advised her to adopt to the ‘thing’, but she could not adjust. Following early sexual abuse, rape, and incest she was sold to Mr_, a widower of four children. Her marriage to Mr _ did little to ease her suffering or oppression; instead, it merely led her into another form of captivity, where she acted as a sex toy and a laborer within the confines of the household. Growing up in such a harrowing environment, she began to think that this was the life for which she had been destined. At this point, she could not imagine anything beyond that existence.

Women in this novel ended up victims of sexism as well as racism. Sofia, a courageous and indomitable spirit, was compelled to surrender to the oppressive power of the whites, both as a woman and as a Black person. She was savagely whipped and thrown into jail, subjected to such brutal treatment that her very identity became unrecognizable. Sheriff concluded “When I see Sofia I don’t know why she still alive. They crack her skull, they crack her ribs. They tear her nose loose on one side. They blind her in one eye. She swole from head to foot. Her tongue the size of my arm, it sticks out tween her teef like a piece of rubber. She can’t talk. And she just about the color of a eggplant” (82). She had renounced her

identity as a resolute individual, embracing instead traits of meekness and passivity.

With Samuel and Corrine, Nettie came to Olinka to start their missionary work. She gave Celie meticulous accounts of their experiences with Olinka culture in her letters. She said Olinka society was deeply patriarchal, with female children barred from school and women economically dependent on their husbands. As Olivia argued that these traditions only served to constrain women's freedom, with a direct parallel to the discouragement of Black girls from schooling in America, where white people sought to deny them an education. Walker highlights the ingrained patriarchal practices in African society as manifest in the Olinkas' life through these observations.

African parents' views are inherently conservative and patriarchal. Women are expected purely to look after the household in Olinka culture at home and primary schooling is reserved for boys. Meanwhile, girls are taught the skills deemed necessary to be good wives. A girl remains the "other", distinct and separate from a boy. Nettie remarked that Tashi's father had a similar attitude to their own father, who resented his daughters' pursuit of education. With this letter, Walker seeks to demonstrate that the oppression of women is a global phenomenon, a common bond of subjugation that transcends geographical boundaries.

Human civilization has consistently relegated nature to an inferior position long ago. The Holy Bible directly declares the superiority of human beings over nature, stating that God has given man "dominion over the fish of the sea and over the birds of the air, and over the cattle, and over all the earth" (qtd in Abrams 72). A similar perspective is evident in the ancient philosophies of Rome and Greece, the Renaissance and the Enlightenment, where human beings wielded the position of apex of beings considering humans as the rulers and masters of nature. This belief ingrains the notion that God created the natural world solely to serve human needs. Consequently, humans exploit natural resources indiscriminately, not to meet their basic necessities, but to gratify their indulgent

desires resulting in environmental degradation which eventually leads to imbalance in delicate balance of the ecosystem.

Walker like other ecofeminists challenges male chauvinism and their dominion over women and nature through the depiction of Olinka culture. Nettie kept Celie informed about her life in Olinka, sharing detailed accounts of the village and its culture. She described Olinka as once being a peaceful African village, rich in natural resources and indigenous traditions. The people lived in a “place without walls but with a leaf roof” (Walker 136), surrounded by “trees and trees and then more trees on top of that. And big. They are so big they look like they were built. And vines. And ferns. And little animals. Frogs. Snakes too” (Walker 135). The native peoples thrived in an ecological setting where nature and mankind lived with each other in peace. However, that ecological balance and mutual respect was disrupted with the arrival of white road builders, who cleared the forests to build new roads by demolishing both animal habitats and human dwellings.

The biological equilibrium was shattered with the loss of these habitats. The people were even forced to buy water from the planters. The expansion of white imperialism extended beyond Olinka to neighboring villages, with the goal of transforming the area into the headquarters of the rubber industry, replacing the forests with rubber trees. Ultimately, capitalism took its firm stance into the rural life, and dismantled the very fabric of the societal life of Olinka village. The traditional culture of Olinka, as indigenous as before, was slowly losing its hold, a casualty of a more and more industrialized society driven into a hole. In the name of modern civilization, the white colonists wreaked untold havoc on the environment.

Walker portrays this dual and simultaneous plight of women and nature within the same oppressive pressures in this novel. Both women and nature are portrayed as the “other,” submissive, exploited, and ruled by men. The novel also stresses the bond that women have with trees; trees are both a sign of redemption and a refuge for women. The protagonist Celie, in her moments of

despair, finds herself in aligned with nature. In a moment of sorrow, she tells herself, “It all I can do not to cry. I make myself wood. I say to myself, Celie, you a tree. That’s how come I know trees fear man” (Walker 23). Here, Celie and trees are depicted on the same platform having emotions and feelings, but incapable of expressing their pain. Shug Avery shares a similar kind of affinity with trees. She believes that trees possess feelings and should be protected, stating, “My first step from the old white man was trees. Then air. Then birds. Then other people. But one day when I was sitting quiet and feeling like a motherless child, which I was, it come to me: that feeling of being part of everything, not separate at all. I knew that if I cut a tree, my arm would bleed” (176).

Women in *The Color Purple* have metamorphosed themselves from the powerless, weak figure into the independent strong woman through drawing strength from the Black sisterhood. Through their unity, they hold power within society as a whole, and they bridge the gap between the ‘other’ and the ‘self’ in society so that they can see who they are and who they wanted to become. The female characters in this novel function as both healers and agents of lifting each other up. As a Black writer, Alice Walker maintains a unique focus, recognizing that the paths of Black women are not directly experienced by White women. Black women, she writes, are subject not just to oppression based on their gender but to the scourge of racism. So, their suffering is not just caused by men, but women as well. In this setting, Black sisterhood becomes an essential support system, a source of strength, solace, and comfort. As Walker tells her story, the women emerge from the myriad forms of oppression endemic to patriarchal society and the sisters who lift up and empower them all.

In the novel, the women realize the transformative power of sisterhood, which allows them to evolve from innocence to maturity, and to liberate themselves from both physical and psychological abuse. With the help of Shug, the protagonist, Celie comes to grasp the true essence of God. At first she passively

suffers the brutality of her husband and resigns herself to a life suffused with pain. But it is from the support of sisterhood, Celie finds the courage to defy her oppressor. She finally resolves to leave her husband, embarking on a new journey to Memphis with Shug, and for the first time reclaiming her own self and identity.

Then I feel Snug shake me. Celie, she say. And I come to myself.

I'm pore, I'm black, I may be ugly and can't cook, a voice say to everything listening. But I'm here. (187)

In this moment, Celie not only leaves her husband but also asserts her independence and discovers her own existence. Her act of resistance emerges when she recognizes the significance of her own selfhood and the rights that belong to her. Celie's transformation represents, in a sense, the awakening of Black women's consciousness and progress. In the village of Olinka the women become increasingly aware of the importance of educating their daughters. Even to face disapproval from society concerning girls being brought up, as they come to realize that education is everything and girls can only be nurtured and blossom by it. Defying patriarchal power, they start sending their daughters to school, intent on shielding them from the constraining influence of male chauvinism.

Every action, however, carries consequences. The changes we make to or disruptions we make to the natural order always leave an imprint on our lives, good or bad. Susan Griffin explores this concept in her influential work *Woman and Nature*:

We say every act comes back on itself. There are consequences. You cannot cut the trees from the mountainside without a flood. We say there is no way to see his dying as separate from her living, or what he had done to her, or what part of her he had used. We say if you change the course of this river you change the shape of the whole place. (Griffin 186)

The relentless exploitation of nature by humankind inevitably invokes nature's wrath, and as a result, mankind finds itself ensnared by its own greed, enduring suffering and hardship. That account of the Olinka people, who get hurt by nature's revenge made by their chief. The Olinka had depended on roofleaf for generations, a sacred guardian that kept the tribe protected from the ravages of rain and wind, sun and heat. It was not only a need that they employed, it was something sacred to them and planted alongside crops like cassava, yam, cotton, millet, and groundnuts. As the chief, however, driven by unquenchable greed, was determined to grow more land, he wished for more ground for crops to trade with the white men who lived near the coast. He took another and another tract and demanded the people take down the roofleaf trees to make way for cassava, millet, and groundnuts. As time passed, the precious roof leaf disappeared, as did the safeguard it afforded. When the rainy season came, a fearsome storm devastated the village and razed the roofs of each of its huts. To their horror, the citizens found that to mend their dwellings, they did not have roofleaf. So, the Olinka suffered a torturous ordeal, an ordeal that is merciless and brutal, that was ripped from them by nature's furious retaliation:

Where roofleaf had flourished from time's beginning, there was cassava. Millet. Groundnuts.

For six months the heavens and the winds abused the people of Olinka. Rain came down in spears, stabbing away the mud of their walls. The wind was so fierce it blew the rocks out of the walls and into the people's cooking pots. Then cold rocks, shaped like millet balls, fell from the sky, striking everyone, men and women and children alike, and giving them fevers. The children fell ill first, then their parents. Soon the village began to die. By the end of the rainy season, half the village was gone. (138)

The Olinka people, who had previously suffered all the fury of nature's retribution against them, were finally stirred into recognition of the importance of their relationship with natural world. Through their suffering, they realized the extent of their

transgressions. In the end, after all, weighed by the evil appetite of his own greed and the havoc it had wrought, the chief was driven to leave the village behind and never to return again. “On the day when all the huts had roofs again from the rootleaf, the villagers celebrated by singing and dancing and telling the story of the rootleaf. The rootleaf became the thing they worship.” (138)

The central theme of ecofeminism in the novel culminates in a vision of wholeness, achieved by the story’s conclusion. Women, once weak and oppressed, evolve into strong and independent figures. Men, women and nature evolve over time into an interconnected, interdependent entity. At the same time, men seem to begin giving a greater respect to both women and nature, undertaking jobs they had never before thought to perform - cleaning, cooking, farming. They shed their old views, and no longer view women as lesser, or ‘other’, but as equals they are experiencing their new world together. Albert specifically is completely different from his former self. He tells Celie, “I’m satisfied this the first time I ever lived on Earth as a natural man. It feels like a new experience” (236). This is his rebirth, as he not only learns to respect women but, more importantly, nature. He nurtures his mental growth in the comfort of nature and when he starts a hobby collecting seashells, a special symbol to signify his individual respect for the natural world.

In the end, the novel unveils a vision of harmonious coexistence - between men and women, humanity and nature, and even between black and white. Celie and Albert, now altered, live as close friends in Celie’s home. Harpo and Sofia reconcile and reunite, while Sofia forms a deep bond with the white mayor’s wife, teaching her to drive. Celie, embracing inclusivity, hires white workers for her shop, and the Olinka people, in reverence for the roofleaf, live in harmony with nature. In this sense, these moments act as reflections of the ethos of wholeness and interconnectedness, which are at the heart of the ecofeminist ideal.

To sum up, as a black feminist, Walker critiques both androcentrism and racism by envisioning a world in which men

and women, black and white, and humanity and nature coexist in harmony. In this novel, she illustrated the main ideas that have shaped her ecofeminist perspective. Walker also showed the natural world as an integrated community where human beings and nature shared mutual respect and close harmony. Through the characters like Celie, Sofia, and Olinka village women, Walker revealed both the systemic oppression of women and the commodification of nature by patriarchal social forces. She explored these representations of women and nature as both 'other' and inferior, belittled by the means of male oppression, the consequences of which will lead to their exploitation. But ultimately both women as well as nature reject these chauvinist attitudes toward men and crave their own independence. From being regarded as the 'Other', they slowly but surely transform into the empowered 'Selves', becoming independent and individual in a society where hierarchical divisions no longer prevail.

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